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How to Future-Proof Careers in Media:

Preparing Undergraduates for an AI-Driven Industry

ABSTRACT

This paper is an exploratory research on how university lecturers can integrate strategic foresight into the syllabus of a media undergraduate course to help students plan their careers in a media industry driven by innovations in Artificial Intelligence (AI). The emergence of AI technologies, particularly generative AI (GenAI) tools for media production, impacts all stages of the media value chain. By implementing strategic foresight techniques, such as scenarios, media organisations learn to embrace change. Thus, strategic foresight is essential for media management as the industry turns into a highly dynamic environment.

The research process consisted in the design and implementation of an undergraduate pilot course (4 ECTS) for sophomore students enrolled in the Crossmedia programme of Tallinn University during the autumn 2024 semester. To pass the course, students had to present a final project based on the strategic planning framework proposed by Amy Webb (2024). The final project included three sections: (1) a self-assessment of their current skills against a current open position in the media industry, (2) a SWOT analysis describing the opportunities and threats AI technologies represent for their desired career path, and (3) a 10-year professional development strategy. Each career plan listed a variety of custom scenarios with short-term tactics, flexible strategies, and a long-term personal vision that considered the impact that AI will have on the

media value chain. The findings from this pilot course suggest that strategic foresight is an effective learning tool that complements the introduction of GenAI technologies in a higher education setting. Future research is needed to define how HEIs and the media industry can collaborate to integrate GenAI technologies and foresight in media professional education programmes, as well to study the implications that the usage of AI represents in terms of sustainability, media ownership, and copyright.

Introduction

“Can machines think?” This question from Alan Turing (1950) is as relevant today as it was when it was first published in the middle of the 20th century. As Artificial Intelligence (AI) becomes a general-purpose technology (Kohler, 2021) that impacts all economic sectors (Arowosegbe, 2024), it is pertinent for the higher education institutions (HEIs) and the media ecosystem to ask: “How can we prepare the next generation of professionals for a media industry in which the value chain is reformulated constantly by the emergence of machines that “seem” to think?”. This paper approached this question with the design and implementation of a pilot course in which students were introduced to AI technologies while also learning about strategic foresight.

Artificial Intelligence (AI)

Artificial Intelligence (AI) is the simulation of intelligence that can imitate the behavioral patterns of humans or any other living entity (Jeffress & Subramanian, 2023). AI can also refer

to the ability of a computer system to obtain, process, rank, synthesise, and generate data, self-correct, and do complex tasks in a human-like way (Aksoy & Kursun, 2024; Arowosegbe et al., 2024; Chan-Olmsted, 2019). From the perspective of systems, Artificial Intelligence is a machine-based system that, based on a set of goals defined by a human, can make predictions, recommendations, or decisions which influence real or virtual environments (Vincent-Lancrin & van der Vlies, 2020). AI is an innovation that is being adopted by different sectors of the economy, with significant effects across industries (Kohler, 2021). Thus, AI can be considered the first general-purpose technology (GPT) to emerge in the 21st century (Connock, 2022).

AI is a collective term which groups cognitive technologies (Connock, 2022), with the following being the top sub-branches: machine learning (ML), neural networks, deep learning, natural language processing (NLP), computer vision, rules based systems, robotic process automation, speech recognition and robots (Chan-Olmsted, 2019). Kulkarni & Bansal (2024) propose that AI technologies can be classified into four major categories: Generative AI (GenAI), Machine Learning (ML), Natural Language Processing (NLP) and Computer Vision.

Table 1. Categorisation of AI sub-branches (Kulkarni & Bansal, 2024)

Artificial Intelligence (AI)	Generative AI (GenAI)	Large Language Model (LLM)
		Multimodal Foundation Model (MFM)
	Machine Learning (ML)	Deep Learning

		Supervised Learning
		Unsupervised Learning
	Natural Language Processing (NLP)	Natural Language Understanding
		Natural Language Generation
		Question and Answering
	Computer Vision	Object Detection
		Scene Understanding
		Face Detection and Recognition
		Motion Analysis
		Text Recognition (OCR)

This paper focuses on generative AI (GenAI) because of its implications for the media value chain, specifically in the creation, bundling, and distribution of content (Hess & Matt, 2013). The popularisation of GenAI as a media production tool began with the introduction of ChatGPT in November 2022. The first iteration of this GenAI chatbot could use short text prompts to write essays and basic code, and by January 2023, the tool reached 100 million users (Nyst, 2024). GenAI applications can now produce media in various formats, including text, image, video, and

audio (Caballero et al., 2025; Connock, 2022; Farinacci, 2024), based on a “prompt” that is a user input designed to generate a specific response from a GenAI application (Aksoy & Kursun, 2024). Beyond producing content based on user inputs, GenAI can also enhance the quality of existing media (Caballero et al., 2025).

Despite its capabilities, Artificial Intelligence, and thus GenAI applications, are not self-aware entities that know what its produced outcomes signify, as human intelligence still is needed to interpret their meaning (Schalk Quintanar & Rooney, 2025). That being said, AI could impact the media value chain in a magnitude similar to the invention of the printing press in the 1400s (De Cremer et al., 2023).

The adoption of AI within the media industry

This paper defines the media industry as the loosely allied class (Connock, 2022) of companies and public entities that provide content for entertainment, information, or educational purposes (Hess & Matt, 2013). The different tasks carried across the value chain are classified by Porter (1985) either as primary and support activities. The first category refers to the creation, bundling, and distribution of content, including its marketing and post-sales services (Chan-Olmsted, 2019; Hess & Matt, 2013). Support activities build the infrastructure that enables the primary ones to happen, with some examples being procurement, human resource management, technological development, and administrative infrastructure (Chan-Olmsted: 2019).

AI is now used across the media value chain, and is used as a tool for content creation, audience analysis, personalisation, data-driven decision-making, and storytelling (Rostamianian & Moradi Kamreh, 2024). Alternatively, Chan-Olmsted (2019) states that the value of AI lies in its power to build the competencies of businesses.

The growing presence of AI within the media value chain cannot be separated from the influence exerted by multinational corporations, power dynamics, and public policies (Farinacci, 2024).

There is no way back to a global media economy without AI technologies. In April 2025, the American Academy of Arts and Sciences confirmed that films that used AI were eligible to receive awards, a resolution made after months of backlash because of the nomination, and eventual win, of Adrian Brody as Best Actor in *The Brutalist*, a film in which AI was used to improve the accent of Brody while he was performing in Hungarian (McMahon, 2025).

The adoption of GenAI applications, such as Runway, Midjourney and Stable Diffusion, allows for the creation of media content with limited resources (Caballero et al. 2025). However, the usage of GenAI for media production brings up the need to address wider implications regarding the use of AI, such as:

- The ownership of media generated using Artificial Intelligence (Aksoy & Kursun, 2024; Caballero et al., 2025).
- Copyright issues (Aksoy & Kursun, 2024).
- The usage of intellectual property as training data for commercial GenAI models (Aksoy & Kursun, 2024; Caballero et al., 2025).

- Bias in AI models (Caballero et al., 2025; Choudhary et al., 2024; Rossi et al., 2025; Vincent-Lancrin & van der Vlies, 2020).
- The lack of transparency regarding AI models, leading to regard them as a “black box” technology. (Connock: 2021)
- Production of inaccurate, biased or misleading content (Meakin, 2024).
- Hallucinations, this is the production of information that is not real. (Aksoy & Kursun, 2024).
- The usage of AI to recreate the audiovisual features of deceased figures (Farinacci, 2024)
- Risks to data privacy (Aksoy & Kursun, 2024).
- Digital divide (Aksoy & Kursun, 2024).
- Impact on the media jobs market (Caballero et al., 2025).
- The carbon footprint generated by the usage of AI applications(Kirkpatrick, 2023).

The adoption of AI follows two decades of a media industry in a continuous state of disruption (Trattner et al., 2022). According to a July 2024 survey by Bectu, the UK’s trade union for the creative industries, 38% of media professionals planned to leave the film and TV industry in the next five years, up from 24% in September 2023 and 37% in February 2024. Women (41%) and nonbinary respondents (38%) planned to leave the industry at a higher rate than men (36%). It is critical to further research how GenAI will affect professional careers in media, identifying roles that are vulnerable to automation and proposing reskilling strategies for media professionals who will be directly impacted (Caballero et al., 2025).

The evolution of AI technologies happens as advancements in biotechnology and connected ecosystems of things are made. Therefore, new media professionals are entering an industry immersed in what Webb (2024) calls “a technology supercycle”, turning them into a “transition generation” since their roles as professionals will be reformulated as further AI innovations are made. De Cremer et al. (2023) propose three scenarios resulting from the adoption of AI in the creative media industries:

1. AI ends supporting humans on their tasks, enabling them to achieve greater efficiency and speed.
2. AI ends suppressing human creativity, due to unfair use of AI-powered algorithms and poor governance. GenAI content drowns human-created media, with professionals opting out of the industry.
3. AI ends causing a “techlash”, a movement in which there is a societal pushback against GenAI content, in which human-made media creations could still be available at a premium.

Rostamian & Moradi Kamreh (2024) point out several issues hindering the adoption of AI in the media industry, including the resistance to change at organisational and cultural levels, the demand for a workforce with specialized skills, the need for continuous training, and skill gaps. Strategic foresight can help to address these issues since it creates and maintains a future-forward view in a changing world.

Strategic Foresight and Scenarios

In a world of continuous technological development, the lack of agency is detrimental for the mental health of individuals (Kohler, 2021). Every human has the capacity of foresight, as it is built into the brain/mind system (Slaughter, 1997). Strategic foresight is a forward view process that enables organisations to detect risks, shape strategy, and create scenarios within a dynamic environment (Slaughter, 1997). Thus, strategic foresight is essential for media management in times of technological disruption, as it stimulates the capability of a business to innovate continuously and embrace change (Constanzo, 2004).

It is also possible to understand strategic foresight as a technique of media ecology that helps to analyze the relationships between technological applications and current media ecosystems, with the capability of evaluating how the adoption of innovations affect media organisations, human communication, society, and the environment (Prasad & Makesh, 2024).

According to Slaughter (1997), strategic foresight requires data from the past and present, in order to view forward and identify relationships. Therefore, strategic foresight enables organisations to not overlook factors that later can overwhelm them as technologies evolve.

Rohrbeck (2012) states that strategic foresight can also help corporations to:

- Detect market trends and technological advancements that imply organisational changes.
- Jumpstart innovation projects.
- Boost innovation and development.
- Create a data system in which strategic decisions can be evaluated.

- Scout new technologies.

Individuals constantly have to take decisions that impact the future, whether they use or not use foresight (Kohler, 2021). Strategic foresight counteracts short term, bottom-line thinking by bringing “the future” to a present decision-making arena. (Slaughter, 1997)..

Strategic foresight is not only an organisational policy tool, it is a practice, an actionable plan, a factor that influences the day-to-day (Slaughter, 1997). Mietzner & Reger (2005) describe how scenario-planning can be a tool to implement strategic foresight and guide decision-making according to potential future environments. By doing so, scenarios open the mind of the individual and the organisation to new possibilities, challenging long-held beliefs, and promoting a culture of change.

Scenarios can be exploratory or normative. Exploratory scenarios map a potential future according to past and present trends. Normative scenarios are anticipatory, as they consider that different choices lead to different visions of the future, with some being less desirable than others (Mietzner & Reger, 2005). Berkhout & Hertin (2002) point out that building scenarios is an activity that follows four principles:

- The future is not a continuation of the past, and it can be affected by choices and actions.
- The future cannot be foreseen, but it can inform decisions in the present.
- There are several potential futures set across a “possibility space”
- Scenario planning is a rational and subjective activity.

Scenarios are generally built in a four-step process: (1) the scope of the scenario is defined, (2) a database is constructed, (3) scenarios are proposed, and (4) strategic decisions are made (Phelps et al., 2001). There are many techniques for scenario building, with one being Amy Webb’s Framework for Strategic Planning (Webb, 2024). In this approach (Figure 1), data or evidence is used to find highly probable outcomes for the next stage, with each section of the cone moving forward in time. The framework begins with actionable tactics, moves to more flexible strategies, and ends with a broader vision of the future.

Figure 1. Framework for Strategic Planning (Webb, 2024)

With the advent of the “technology supercycle” (Webb, 2024), there is a need to promote strategic decision-making and strategic foresight tools, yet the educational investment in them is modest (Kohler, 2021). Strategic foresight could be a valuable asset not only for media

companies but also for the next generation of professionals, as it leads to the creation of a common approach for dealing with future issues (Mietzner and Reger, 2005).

Integrating strategic foresight and GenAI tools in higher education (HE)

Paraphrasing Damásio (2024) posture on integration of new technologies in film schools, overcoming the challenge of adopting AI in media degree programmes is crucial to provide a relevant and inclusive education. In Higher Education Institutions (HEIs), AI has the potential to revolutionize the roles and activities of students, lecturers, and institutions (Denecke et al., 2023). Thus, a human-centric innovation approach towards the integration of AI is necessary, to make it into a source of innovation which HEIs can leverage (Damásio, 2024).

Integrating GenAI into education involves students, faculty, and the educational system (Bozkurt, 2023). GenAI can tailor course materials, grade assignments, offer self-directed learning, and assist in academic writing (Meakin, 2024). The adoption of AI in HEIs is happening at a fast pace. In a 2023 worldwide survey among HE students and lecturers, over 80% of participants used AI applications such as Google Translate, ChatGPT, and DeepL (Denecke et al., 2023).

A potential way to understand how to integrate AI technologies and foresight into the syllabus of a media undergraduate course can be learned from audiovisual education. For over two decades, audiovisual education has long followed a three-tier model: educating *through* media, educating

about media and educating *within* the media. This model is further enriched by the inclusion of *aesthetics*, *ethics* and *critique* and dimensions of media (Farinacci, 2024).

Higher education students should be capable of recognizing the tool capabilities of GenAI, instead of using it as a source of knowledge or authority (Meakin, 2024). The integration of new technologies requires future media professionals not only to understand the relationships between the formal elements of media, but also having a deeper understanding on how meaning is created through manipulative processes, and its connection to the real world (Damásio, 2024).

Just like in the media industry, there are concerns regarding AI technologies being used to fulfill roles currently occupied by humans in the education sector. This fear denotes both the need for faculty development opportunities to reduce resistance to change, and the need to include educators in the design of technological integration plans that impact them (Choudhary et al., 2024). There are also concerns regarding students not developing critical thinking and problem-solving skills as they become dependent on GenAI to do research and fulfill study requirements (Meakin, 2024). Choudhary (2024) proposes the following recommendations for integrating AI in education:

1. Institutions should invest in AI training programs for educators.
2. Stringent data privacy protocols should be followed to protect the data from students and the institution.
3. AI tools should be accessible to all students, no matter their financial situation or technological background.
4. The use of AI in research should aim to fasten data analysis and innovation.

5. Feedback loops should be developed to improve AI tools that personalize learning.
6. AI should complement human educators, not replace them.
7. Ethical guidelines must be established and implemented to ensure a fair use of AI technologies and reduce AI bias.

From a practical perspective, the principles of toolkit design for strategic technology management (Kerr et al., 2013) can be quite useful for Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) as they work on including GenAI content production and strategic foresight in their media degree programmes. These principles are:

1. The strategy should be human-centric, allowing users to collaborate by supporting social interaction and aid decision making.
2. Using a workshop-based approach to provide opportunities for group interactions.
3. The facilitator should focus on the learning process, acting from a neutral perspective.
4. Using tools during the workshop should allow users to “start small, and iterate fast”.
5. The integration of tools should be modular, with the final output being the result of using the tools, in a composite form.
6. The tools should be employed at different levels within the organisational structure.
7. Visual support is necessary to show the application of tools, and their resulting outputs for reporting and communication purposes.

Methodology

The exploratory research encompassed the design and implementation of an undergraduate pilot course (4 ECTS) as part of the second-year study offer of the Crossmedia undergraduate programme at Tallinn University. 20 sophomore students were automatically enrolled in the course, with two additional students signing up to attend the class on a volunteer basis—1 student from the Digital Learning Games MA and 1 recent Crossmedia graduate. The course took place in an in-person format, with 10 lectures and 3 final project review days taking place between September 2024 and January 2025. To complete the course and obtain their credits, students had to prepare a final project. The final project featured three sections: (1) a self-assessment of their current skills against a current open position in the media industry, (2) a SWOT analysis describing the opportunities and threats AI technologies represent for their desired career path, and (3) a 10-year professional development strategy based on the strategic planning framework by Webb (2024). Each career plan listed a variety of custom scenarios with short-term tactics, flexible strategies, and a long-term personal vision that considered the impact that AI will have on the media value chain and their own careers in the industry.

To reduce the possibility of students becoming dependent on GenAI, written essays and online quizzes were removed from the syllabus. Instead, a “flipped” classroom approach was used to replace written assignments, in which students were required to make a 5-minute presentation about an GenAI application or AI technology they found interesting. Class time was split between theory and practice: 70% of the course time was dedicated to lectures and 30% to practical experimentation with GenAI to create media (text, video, image, sound) under the

supervision of the lecturer. It is pertinent to mention that the GenAI tools used were not open source and included pay-to-generate and subscription-based applications such as Kling, Midjourney, Runway, Suno, ElevenLabs, ChatGPT, among others. The lectures were designed following the triple-tiered approach towards media education (Farinacci, 2024) and covered the following topics:

- The concept of Artificial Intelligence and its history.
- Data, databases, and data sources.
- Uncertainty and Reasoning from the perspective of AI.
- Search and Games in AI.
- Role of Algorithms in AI.
- Natural Language Processing (NLP).
- Media production using GenAI.
- Ethical use of AI and AI biases.
- Robots.
- Machine Learning.
- Deep Learning & Neural Networks.

All course participants were 18 years and above. Pre-course and post-course surveys were conducted to measure student familiarity with GenAI tools and gather student feedback. The surveys were designed using AidaForms, were voluntary and anonymous in compliance with GDPR. Only participants willing to answer the survey did so, with 18 initial surveys and 14 post-course surveys collected.

Findings

Among the 18 course participants who completed the pre-course survey, 33% stated they had never used Artificial Intelligence to produce images before, a number reduced to zero by the end of the course. 21 participants were Crossmedia BA students (with 1 being a recent graduate), which implied that they had an interdisciplinary background. 17 students reported interest in following a specific career path, with answers varying between Film and Media Production (6), Art and Design (2), Advertising and Social media (2), Entrepreneurship (2), Education (1), Extended Reality and Video Games (2), Music (1) and Homemaking (1). One student stated they were undecided regarding their career path, but that they were using their Crossmedia studies to figure it out. The 22 enrolled students completed the final project requirement and thus passed the course.

The practices during class hours allowed students to experiment with a variety of GenAI tools under the supervision of the lecturer. The instructions for each practice encouraged students to make their own prompts. For example, during the practice with ChatGPT as a tool to generate text, students were instructed to “ask ChatGPT to re-tell the story of The Little Red Riding Hood, at least changing the location and the time in which the story was set” with the student being responsible for selecting the new location and time-setting of the story while having the possibility to further specifying their prompt.

It is pertinent to note that during text-to-image experimentation, students used a single computer (mirrored with a tablet which was passed along) to enter prompts in order to facilitate

supervision. The resulting GenAI media were projected onto the classroom screen. On two occasions, both during text-to-image experimentation using MidJourney, the lecturer had to pause and discuss the limitations of GenAI. Data and model bias were discussed after a trans student was misgendered while trying to generate a virtual portrait of themselves. The second time, the concept of AI self-policing and user abuse was addressed after a student generated the image of a heavily pregnant woman being pushed down the stairs as they tested which prompts MidJourney refused to process.

Besides the lectures, three class days were reserved for project evaluation. Students were asked to present their project in stages to receive feedback, following the approach to “start small, iterate fast” (Kerr et al, 2013).

The pilot course received positive feedback, with 3 students reporting making career decisions as a result from making their career plan using strategic foresight. Post-course survey participants (14) reported a deeper understanding of the concept of AI, its applications, societal and ethical impact, and its role in their personal future.

Table 2. Post-course feedback regarding the undergraduate pilot course

Topic	Key Themes	Example Quotes
Concept of Artificial Intelligence	Basic concepts, classifications, internal	<i>"I learned basic concepts, different types, and applications of AI in text, image, video and other kinds of media."</i>

	operation, and workflows of AI.	<p><i>"General data and probability was interesting."</i></p> <p><i>"(I learned)The general concept of AI workflow. The way data is processed in different tools and how it uses and generates it."</i></p>
	History of AI	<i>"All the fundamentals about AI, starting from the history and ending with AI tools that influence our studies, life and work."</i>
AI Tools	Use of GenAI in research and education.	<i>"I also learned about new AI tools to use, which have been very helpful (NotebookLM for example)."</i>
	Use of GenAI in creative media.	<p><i>"Interesting to see how AI tools are used in the creative field."</i></p> <p><i>"It's definitely gonna make some homework video creating easier."</i></p> <p><i>"Before this class I had known only about the ChatGPT. But now I feel that I have much more knowledge."</i></p>

Societal & Ethical Impacts	AI lack of regulation, loss of jobs due to GenAI adoption.	<p><i>"(I learned) how serious will be the AI impact on our future."</i></p> <p><i>"(I learned) how little is really done now about it (AI) because development is faster than lawmaking."</i></p> <p><i>"Voice actors might lose their job."</i></p>
	Ethical issues, such as bias	<i>"(I learned) the level of trustworthiness in AI tools and the bias different AI data sets might have now."</i>
	Recognition of the role of humans	<p><i>"AI cannot replace the energy of the actor."</i></p> <p><i>"AI can't really replace human emotions and feelings."</i></p>
Impact of AI in Personal Life and Mental Health	Awareness of how AI impacts daily life	<i>"It makes me understand better how everything online works."</i>
	Loss of fear towards AI,	<p><i>"(I learned) how we can make AI work for our benefit instead of being scared it"</i></p> <p><i>"AI isn't so scary and the future might not be doomed (still think it is but I am a pessimist)."</i></p>
Personal Enjoyment	Enjoyment in participating in the course	<i>"I loved also acting part and you explained well how I could use it."</i>

		<p><i>"I loved all the actual examples of tools and actings."</i></p> <p><i>"It was fun to see this (GenAI) voice tool."</i></p>
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Among the suggestions received for improvement were more time to practice with GenAI tools (5), more home assignments (2), clearer assignment instructions (1), changing the course time from morning to afternoon (1), and making attendance mandatory (1).

Discussion

The findings of this exploratory pilot suggest that including strategic foresight as part of GenAI undergraduate course provides a positive educational experience for future media professionals. It is important to teach students how to use GenAI tools to remove the “black box notion” that surrounds it (Connock, 2021), while also providing them with a deeper understanding on how AI impacts the activities of the media industry (Chan-Olmsted, 2019; Hess & Matt, 2013), its biases (Meakin, 2024), and its impact on the media jobs market (Caballero et al., 2025).

Strategic foresight was useful to provide a sense of agency among students, which is crucial for their mental health within a world in technological evolution (Kohler, 2021). The “flipped classroom” approach, allowed students to enrich the variety of GenAI tools explored within a classroom setting. In a group of 22 participants, each of them presented a different AI application without repeating. That being said, it further shows how big the challenge of upskilling is for an educator within a media programme (Choudhary, 2024). The choice of GenAI applications for

media creation is ever-expanding, with each of them following a specific workflow, pointing out the need to research how educators can select the tools in which they will become proficient in order to teach its use to their students.

The pilot suggests the need to prepare lecturers to address the limitations of AI technology when areas for improvement are identified, such as copyright issues (Aksoy & Kursun, 2024), bias in AI models (Caballero et al., 2025; Choudhary et al., 2024; Rossi et al., 2025; Vincent-Lancrin & van der Vlies, 2020), the carbon footprint generated by the usage of AI applications (Kirkpatrick, 2023). and the production of inaccurate, biased or misleading content (Meakin, 2024).

While not a focus of this paper, budget may be a limitation for the adoption of GenAI tools, as many work on a pay-for-generation basis. One option for media HEIs is to make strategic partnerships with GenAI companies, like NYU Tisch School of the Arts did with Runway (Runway, 2024). Another alternative is for HEIs to promote the use of in-house GenAI tools built using open models and databases, with the aim of having full ownership and reducing software costs. This would entail further research to study how in-house GenAI models compare to private GenAI tools as learning tools within a media higher education programme.

Conclusions

The findings from this exploratory pilot course suggest that teaching strategic foresight to future media professionals will be useful to support the activities of media management as the value chain reinvents itself as novel AI-based technologies, solutions, and media applications emerge..

Strategic foresight enriches the learning process by allowing students to make sense of their future careers in the media industry as it evolves alongside AI. If future research on strategic foresight within the media industry validates this, it is possible to create a more comprehensive case regarding the inclusion of strategic foresight in media degree programmes. This could be extremely useful for Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) who need to reformulate media curricula while still attempting to adopt new AI applications across other disciplines and its own internal processes. More comprehensive research is also needed to address how the media industry and HEIs can collaboratively use strategic foresight and scenarios to reformulate the roles of media professionals and prepare a common core curriculum that includes the skills demanded by these revamped roles. While the future of an AI-driven media industry is not possible to predict, this paper encourages the nurturing of foresight skills in the next generation of media professionals so they are prepared to build careers within a dynamic environment.

Keywords: genai, ai, strategic foresight, scenarios, media management

Disclosure statement regarding the use of Artificial Intelligence (AI)

The text and images contained in this paper were not generated using Generative Artificial Intelligence (GenAI) applications. ChatGPT was used to categorize the pre-course and post-survey data. The author proofread this article using ProWritingAid, an application that uses AI to identify errors and suggest corrections.

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